

HAUT

A Multidisciplinary Peer-Reviewed Journal

ISSN: 0938-2216 | Impact Factor: 4.12

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Dear Author,

We are pleased to inform you that your submitted manuscript titled: **“Integrating Intellectual Property Rights, Traditional Knowledge Systems, and the Evolution of Ayurveda: A Multidisciplinary Examination”** has been accepted for publication in the Haut following a favorable review.

Manuscript ID: HAUTR2911

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- The publication fee is non-refundable under all circumstances.
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- We congratulate you on your acceptance and look forward to your continued scholarly contributions.

Date: 13-12-2025

Sincerely,
Editorial Office
Taesam Zhang

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